

Joint INTEGRAL-Swift Target of Opportunity Observations of the Extreme TeV-Detected Blazar Markarian 501

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BL Lacertae Objects

- **Blazar subclass: AGNs of elliptical galaxies** with
 - Non-thermal continuum emission stretching from radio to TeV band (17-19 orders of frequency)
 - Absence of emission lines
 - Strong flux variability in all spectral bands
 - Compact and flat-spectrum radio emission
 - Apparent superluminal motion of some components
 - High and variable radio/optical polarization
 - Strong X-ray and γ -ray emissions: BLLs - a majority of extragalactic TeV sources and one of the most important constituent of Fermi-LAT catalogues
- **Hypothetic structure:** central supermassive BH (SMBH; 10^8 - $10^9 M_{\odot}$) + accretion disc (AD) + two opposite jets (closely aligned to the observer)
- **Open problems:**
 - jet launching mechanisms
 - particle acceleration processes in BL Lac jets
 - Particle content
 - Emission processes for the SED higher-energy component (SSC/ES/hadronic)
 - Origin of MWL variability

Mrk 501
Swift-XRT Exposure: 0 s

Mrk 501: in Brief

- R.A.: 16 53 52.2 (hh mm ss)
Dec.: +39 45 37 (dd mm ss)
- Redshift: $z=0.034$ or 9915 ± 25 km/s
- Distance: 456 Mly (140 Mpc)
- Bright X-ray source and the second extragalactic object detected in the TeV band (Quinn+1996)
- SMBH of $(0.9 - 3.4) \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$
- Radio jet: 120 to 200 kpc
- Intranight flux variability with flux-doubling times down to 2 minutes was observed with MAGIC during the two most active nights (2005 June 30 and July 9; Albert+2007);
- Variability by a factor of 30 with ~ 8 times brighter than the Crab Nebula during the dramatic TeV-band activity in 1997 March-October (Protheroe +1997) Meanwhile, the synchrotron peak underwent a shift towards to energies of 100 keV (Pian+1998).
- the first detection of gamma rays from an extragalactic source well beyond 10 TeV, up to ~ 20 TeV (Aharonian+2001; "overwhelmed" only in 2019, by Crab nebula making it the first identified source beyond 100 TeV)

- **Mrk 501**: HBL source (synchrotron SED peak at UV—X-ray frequencies)

sed1653p3945 Ra=253.46754 deg Dec=39.76017 deg (NH=1.6E20 cm⁻²)

- **Mrk 501**: frequent target for Swift-XRT

Swift

- **Scientific Instruments:**

- ✓ **Burst Alert Telescope** (BAT, 15-250 keV) with a wide FOV (2 steradians) coded-aperture gamma ray with arc-minute positional accuracy
- ✓ **X-ray Telescope** (XRT)

Property	Description
Telescope	JET-X Wolter I
Focal Length	3.5 m
Effective Area	110 cm ² @ 1.5 keV
Telescope PSF	18 arcsec HPD @ 1.5 keV
Detector	EEV CCD-22, 600 x 600 pixels
Detector Operation	Imaging, Timing, and Photon-counting
Detection Element	40 x 40 micron pixels
Pixel Scale	2.36 arcsec/pixel
Energy Range	0.2-10 keV
Sensitivity	2 x 10 ⁻¹⁴ erg cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ in 10 ⁴ seconds

- ✓ **UltraViolet/Optical Telescope** (UVOT, 1700 – 6500 Å)

Filter Central Wavelength (Å)

v	5468
b	4392
u	3465
uvw1	2600
uvm2	2246
uvw2	1928

- **In the past:** significantly enhanced 0.3-10 keV activity during 2013-2015, peaking in 2014 March--October

The prolonged X-ray flaring activity of Mrk 501 in 2014

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ABSTRACT

The X-ray variability of the BL Lacertae source Mrk 501 was studied during 11.5 yr of monitoring with *Swift*. Here, we report the results of this study pertaining to the epoch of 2014 March–October, when our target showed the most powerful and long-lasting X-ray flaring activity. This epoch was characterized by X-ray flares varying in amplitude by factors of 2–5 on time-scales of a few weeks or shorter. We detected 35 instances of the intraday variability, sometimes occurring within the 1 ks observational runs. The X-ray flux was generally correlated with the TeV flux, while the 0.3–300 GeV and optical-UV fluxes did not show a significant correlation. Some notable incidences of more complicated variability patterns could also be recognized, indicating that the high-energy emission in Mrk 501 arose from an emission region more complex than a single zone. The best fits of the 0.3–10 keV spectra were mainly obtained using the logparabola model. Strong spectral variability was detected, affecting the slope but not the curvature of the spectrum. In strong flares, the spectral index became harder than 1.70. The spectral evolution was characterized by a harder-when-brighter behaviour, shifting the peak of the spectral energy distribution by about 20 keV that happens rarely in blazars.

Nowadays: another cycle of long-term X-ray flare (starting since 2021 March; Kapanadze, B. Atel#15477, 15134, 15124, 15059) → **Long-term increase of jet collimation rate?** → **Long-term (up to decade-long) instable processes in accretion disc?**

- Intense Target of Opportunity (TOO) observations with Swift (David Paneque, Bidzina Kapanadze, Abe Falcone; <https://www.swift.psu.edu/toop/summary.php>)
- Active TOO cycle (tentative schedule):

#	Window Start	Window Stop	XRT Mode	UVOT Mode	Exposure (s)
1	2022-10-19 00:00:00	2022-10-20 00:00:00	WT	0x30ed	1000
2	2022-10-23 00:00:00	2022-10-24 00:00:00	WT	0x30ed	1000
3	2022-10-27 00:00:00	2022-10-28 00:00:00	WT	0x30ed	1000
4	2022-10-31 00:00:00	2022-11-01 00:00:00	WT	0x30ed	1000
5	2022-11-04 00:00:00	2022-11-05 00:00:00	WT	0x30ed	1000
6	2022-11-08 00:00:00	2022-11-09 00:00:00	WT	0x30ed	1000

- Swift Target of opportunity (ToO) observations (55% of Swift's observing time): unique opportunity for detailed study of X-ray flux and spectral variability, searching for the correlation of different spectral parameters for the particular flare
- **To date, up to 220 my TOO requests for >20 blazars are approved** by Swift Science Operations Team, revealing a number of X-ray flares of BL Lacs (along with those submitted by other proposers)

- **The 2021-2022 Flare:** Swift Results

- Up to 160 Swift visits to Mrk 501 since 2021 March (out of 920 since 2005 February)

- Number of 0.3-10 keV intraday variability down to **subhour timescales** revealed (Swift-XRT snapshots)

- X-ray spectra of HBLs (BL Lacs with synchrotron peaks at UV—X-ray frequencies): generally **curved**, predominantly fitted with the **logparabolic** model (LP, Massaro+2004)

$$F(E) = K(E/E_1)^{-(a+b \log(E/E_1))} \quad \text{ph/cm}^2/\text{s}$$

with K: normalization factor

E_1 : reference energy, fixed to 1 keV

a : photon index at 1 keV

b : curvature parameter

The position of the synchrotron SED peak (Massaro+2004):

$$E_p = E_1 10^{(2-a)/2b} \quad \text{keV}$$

X-Ray spectral curvature

- **Comparable curvatures observed during the current and 2014 flares:**

✓ $\Delta b = 0.32(0.06)$ vs $\Delta b = 0.34(0.06)$

✓ $\bar{b} = 0.19(0.01)$ with $b_{max} = 0.41(0.11)$ vs $\bar{b} = 0.21(0.01)$ with $b_{max} = 0.42(0.06)$

- **However,**

- ✓ **More frequent observation of powerlaw spectra:**

❖ **38% vs 23% in 2014**

- **Synchrotron SED expected** (Massaro+ 2011)

➤ relatively broader (i.e., lower curvature, $b \sim 0.3$ or smaller) when the efficient stochastic acceleration is at work in the blazar jet → **operating in the turbulent jet area which accelerates particles using scattering centers moving relative to each other even without differences in the actual flow speed**

- **Relativistic shocks in BL Lac jets: turbulent structures can be strongly amplified in shocked material** (Marcher 2014, Mizuno+2014)

- **Alfvén waves in the turbulent downstream of a relativistic shock: can provide promising conditions for efficient stochastic acceleration** (Virtanen & Vainio 2005)

- **Stochastic process: not tied to the plasma speed → continue to accelerate particles far away from the shock and for much longer than the first-order process – provided there is sufficient turbulence present** (Tammi & Duffy 2009)

- 0.3-10 keV Spectra: **Photon Index and synchrotron SED peak position**

- Wider range of spectral indices:**
 - ✓ $\Delta a = 0.44(0.03)$ vs $\Delta a = 0.63(0.04)$
 - ✓ $\Delta \Gamma = 0.52(0.03)$ vs $\Delta \Gamma = 0.44(0.03)$
- On average, softer spectra:**
 - ✓ $\bar{a} = 1.92$ with $a_{min} = 1.70(0.03)$ vs $\bar{a} = 1.70$ with $a_{min} = 1.39(0.06)$
 - ✓ $\bar{\Gamma} = 2.09$ with $\Gamma_{min} = 1.84(0.01)$ vs $\bar{\Gamma} = 1.78$ with $\Gamma_{min} = 1.54(0.02)$

- Hard powerlaw spectra: Relativistic magnetic reconnection (Christie+2019)**
- Powerlaw spectra in general: first-order Fermi acceleration at relativistic shock front when electrons are not confined by magnetic field with a confinement efficiency decreasing with particle's energy (Massaro+2004) → More frequent presence of the jet magnetic field with such a property**

$$\bar{E}_p = 2.31(0.10) \text{ with } E_{p_{max}} = 10.93(1.26) \text{ vs}$$

$$\bar{E}_p = 6.00(0.07) \text{ with } E_{p_{max}} = 20.96(2.81)$$

- Fewer "populated" highest-energy tail of the electron energy distribution during the ongoing flaring activity**

- **Softer spectra → lower unabsorbed 0.3-10 keV fluxes:**
 - ✓ $\bar{F} = 2.65(0.01)e-10$ cgs vs $\bar{F} = 4.18(0.01)e-10$ in 2014
 - ✓ $F_{max} = 5.21(0.04)e-10$ cgs vs $F_{max} = 8.22(0.05)e-10$
- Although higher maximum 0.3-10 count rate during the ongoing flare, the corresponding spectrum - very soft ($\Gamma = 2.36 \pm 0.03$) → injection of freshly accelerated “soft” electron population? →
- Weaker “harder-when-brighter” spectral evolution than in 2014
- Some physical “agents” preventing electrons to “settle down” PED’s highest-energy tail
 - ✓ Weaker magnetic fields?
 - ✓ Weaker turbulence?

INTEGRAL Results

- INTEGRAL TOO requests have been regularly prepared by Elena Pian (initially triggered by my Atel ##15059 posted on 2021 November 23)
- Required for INTEGRAL trigger: the 0.3-10 keV flux $> 2.5 \times 10^{-10}$ cgs (from Swift-XRT observations; corresponding to ~ 10 mCrab)
- Mrk 501 detected at 6 sigma with CR=0.48 cts/s

Image (30-100 keV): mosaic of Revs 2538+2539+2544+2545+2549+2550+2555+2556 (provided by Mariateresa Fiocchi)

- **IBIS-band flux From Rev 2538+2539+2544+2545+2549+2550:**

$$F(30-100 \text{ keV}) = (2.4 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{-11} \text{ cgs}$$

- **The IBIS-band spectral points derived at the energies of 41.5 \pm 11.5 keV and 77.5 \pm 24.5 (replenishing those obtained with Swift-XRT, Swift-UVOT, Tuorla (optical R-band), Fermi-LAT (300 MeV – 300 GeV) and MAGIC (VHE))**

30-100 keV light curve (provided by Mariateresa Fiocchi)

Swift-BAT observations: no strong flaring activity

- no detection with 5σ (1-d binned data) and 7 detections with 3σ
- The 2014 March—October period
 - ✓ frequent detections with 5σ and clearly-expressed long-term 15-150 keV flare (Kapanadze+2017)

Tuorla observations:

- Relatively elevated R-band states (although, not so much as in 0.3-10 keV energy range)

TELAMON (Efelsberg) observations:

- No prominent radio flare

Radio observations of MRK 501 in the framework of the TELAMON programme (provided by Matthias Kadler)

Fermi-LAT 300 MeV – 300 GeV:

- **No significant difference from the states observed during previous years (similar situation in the VHE energy range; David Paneque, private communications)**

Summary and Conclusions

- **Mrk 501 – one of the most extreme particle accelerators among HBLs**
 - ✓ - Bright source in the X-ray band where the injection and radiative evolution of freshly accelerated particles can be tracked (particularly, during the strong long-term X-ray flares in 2014 and 2021-2022 (still ongoing!))
 - ✓ - flux and spectral variability can be detected within a few hundred seconds (0.3-10 keV and TeV energy ranges)
- **Long-term 0.3-10 keV flaring activity since 2021 March:** general elevated 0.3-10 keV state superimposed by those of 2-4 weekly timescales
 - ✓ Major additional mechanisms: first and second order Fermi mechanisms, related to the propagation of relativistic shocks and turbulent structures in the jets (corroborated by the observed log-parabolic X-ray and gamma-ray spectra)
 - ✓ The features of second-order Fermi (stochastic) acceleration are observed more frequently than those of energy-dependent acceleration probability process (EDAP, a variety of first-order Fermi mechanism)
- **Future plans:**
 - ✓ Construction of broadband SEDs and modelling by using different emission models (synchrotron + SC/EC/hadronic)
 - ✓ Observations with Swift, MAGIC, Fermi, TELAMON (ongoing)
 - ✓ Joint publication devoted to the ongoing X-ray flaring activity
 - ✓ Further INTEGRAL TOO observations encouraged!

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Thanks! მადლობა!